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ABSTRACT

Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) have been studied as rheological modulator in order to improve the printing performance of a novel polycaprolactone-polyethylene glycol (PCL-PEG) waterborne polyurethane urea (WBPUU) based ink for direct ink writing 3D-printing technology. The cellulose nanocrystals are chemically bonded to the WBPU, since they were added during the synthesis of a WBPUU, in order to tune the rheological properties of the ink and thus, improve the printing performances. The WBPUU- CNC inks have been extensively characterized from the rheological viewpoint and have been subsequently used to print different pieces. To determine the capacity of the CNC to improve the printing performance of this type of inks, we establish the relationship between the rheological properties of the inks and their printing viability by an optimal window of compositions of the inks. Additionally, we have measured the mechanical and thermomechanical properties of printed WBPUU-CNC pieces to evaluate the effective reinforcement of in situ incorporated CNC in the WBPUU-CNC inks. The results showed that the addition of CNC accentuates the shear-thinning behaviour, presenting lower $\tan \delta$, especially at the lowest CNC contents compared with the matrix, which resulted in inks with excellent printable properties. Moreover, the shape fidelity is increased by the solid-like behavior due to the filler effect of CNC and confirmed by SEM images. Finally, a large increase in Young's modulus and thermal and thermomechanical stability were observed on the printed pieces that contained only 0.5 wt% CNC compared to the matrix, suggesting the formation of effective interactions between CNC and WBPUU, as corroborated by FTIR, that lead to a greater reinforcement.

Keywords:

Cellulose nanocrystals · Waterborne polyurethane urea · 3D-printing · Shape fidelity · Printability

Role of in situ added cellulose nanocrystals as rheological modulator of novel waterborne polyurethane urea for 3D- printing technology

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ABSTRACT

Abstract Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) have been studied as rheological modulator in order to improve the printing performance of a novel polycaprolactone-polyethylene glycol (PCL-PEG) waterborne polyurethane urea (WBPUU) based ink for direct ink writing 3D-printing technology. The cellulose nanocrystals are chemically bonded to the WBPU, since they were added during the synthesis of a WBPUU, in order to tune the rheological properties of the ink and thus, improve the printing performances. The WBPUU- CNC inks have been extensively characterized from the rheological viewpoint and have been subsequently used to print different pieces. To determine the capacity of the CNC to improve the printing performance of this type of inks, we establish the relationship between the rheological properties of the inks and their printing viability by an optimal window of compositions of the inks. Additionally, we have measured the mechanical and thermomechanical properties of printed WBPUU-CNC pieces to evaluate the effective reinforcement of in situ incorporated CNC in the WBPUU-CNC inks. The results showed that the addition of CNC accentuates the shear-thinning behaviour, presenting lower $\tan \delta$, especially at the lowest CNC contents compared with the matrix, which resulted in inks with excellent printable properties. Moreover, the shape fidelity is increased by the solid-like behavior due to the filler effect of CNC and confirmed by SEM images. Finally, a large increase in Young's modulus and thermal and thermomechanical stability were observed on the printed pieces that contained only 0.5 wt% CNC compared to the matrix, suggesting the formation of effective interactions between CNC and WBPUU, as corroborated by FTIR, that lead to a greater reinforcement.

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INTRODUCTION

The novel direct ink writing 3D-printing (DIW) is gaining increasing interest in several fields due to the possibility of design complex devices overcoming drawbacks of the classic 3D-printing, among others, the use of volatile organic compounds and higher printing temperatures. This printing technique, also referred as micro-extrusion (Murphy and Atala 2014), has been developed from the conventional fused layer deposition modeling, and consists of the extrusion

of a material, also known as ink, through a needle pushed by a pneumatic pressure, a piston, or a rotating screw (Visser et al. 2013; Kang et al. 2016). By this way, a continuous and homogenous thread is formed which can be shaped forming 3D complex designs with high resolution.

There is a wide variety of materials to consider as printing materials or inks. Concretely, according to the related literature, the DIW 3D-printing technology allows the extrusion of high viscosity solutions, hydrogels, colloidal suspensions, cell suspensions and aggregates, with or without a carrier (Ozbolat and Hospodiuk 2015). Gelation methods including physical (Arai et al. 2011), chemical and photo-crosslinking (Cui et al. 2012) are used to ensure the stability of printed constructs. Among hydrogels based inks for DIW 3D-printing technology, alginate based inks have been extensively studied in the last years (Tirella et al. 2009; Li et al. 2016; Wu et al. 2016; Luo et al. 2018) due to their shear-thinning behaviour as well as owing to their good shape fidelity after crosslinking with Ca^{2+} ions (Pan et al. 2016; Bendtsen et al. 2017). However, printable inks based in other type of hydrogels have been also proposed by different authors (Hockaday et al. 2012; Hung et al. 2016; Rutz et al. 2019). Cellulose, both under nanofibers (CNF) and nanocrystals (CNC) structures have been also studied by many authors as a potential material for printing (Siqueira et al. 2017), but also as additives to alginate or other hydrogels based inks (Hong 2015; Nguyen et al. 2017).

In this context, the fine-tune of the ink formulation appears as an important way in order to achieve the best printing performances. As previously mentioned, multiple materials have been used as ink for printing, but the design of these materials still exhibits some difficulties. One of the major limitation of most of the hydrogels based inks are the inadequate mechanical properties of the printed pieces (Calvert 2009). In this context, the incorporation of reinforcements has been the most followed strategy (Shin et al. 2012; Iviglia et al. 2016; Kosik-Kozioł et al. 2017). Moreover, the influence of the addition of different types of fillers as rheological modulators has been also studied. Li et al. studied the influence of the addition of graphene oxide into alginate based hydrogels and demonstrated an improvement of the recovery of the viscosity in hydrogels with small amounts of graphene oxide (Li et al. 2016). Some authors proposed CNF in order to reinforce an alginate based bio-ink, obtaining an improvement of the shape fidelity as well as the apparition of the shear-thinning behavior (Markstedt et al. 2015). Generally this technology allows to give access to a wide printing viscosity range from 30 to 6×10^7 mPa s (Gudupati et al. 2016), nevertheless, the inks have to satisfy other rheological criteria in order to be suitable materials for printing.

The suitable inks must present a decrease of the viscosity with the increase of the shear rate (shear thinning behaviour) to be successfully extruded, but at the same time they have to be able to recover it rapidly and to maintain the given shape supporting the multi-layer 3D structure. So as to evaluate the viability of the inks for DIW 3D-printing, authors are agreed to explore (i) the “printability” of the ink, or in other words its processability and (ii) the shape fidelity and integrity of the printed construct to self-sustain a 3D multi-layered construct, according to the rheological properties of the inks. Regarding the printability, the target materials to satisfy these criteria are well-known pseudoplastic fluids with shear-thinning behaviour which presented a well-defined yield point (Thibaut et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2020). For the determination of the yield point, many authors propose to measure rheological properties and establish a relationship with the process parameters (Shih et al. 2004; Graef et al. 2011; Sharma et al. 2017). Contrary,

the capacity of the ink to maintain the given shape as well as to support multiple layers is linked to the storage modulus and $\tan \delta$ [loss modulus (G'')/storage modulus (G')] values derived from the spectromechanical analysis. High values of storage modulus and low ones of $\tan \delta$ are correlated to highly structured systems that result in inks with good shape fidelity, which can also support multiple layers without collapsing. However, very low $\tan \delta$ values can result in adhesion problems between layers, due the increase of the elastic behaviour, resulting in a poor printing performance.

Thus, this work proposes the study of the role of the cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) as viscosity modulator and its influence on the printing performance of a novel waterborne polyurethane urea (WBPUU) dispersions based on the combination of hydrophobic polycaprolactone (PCL) and hydrophilic polyethyleneglycol (PEG), as well as the shape fidelity of the final printing objects. Despite other works using WBPUU based inks have been published recently as 3D-printing materials (Hung et al. 2014, 2016; Chen et al. 2019), none of them use the combination of PEG and PCL as the soft segment of the polyurethane so as to ease the physical gelation. In order to improve the printing performance of this WBPUU inks, CNC were added to the ink by in situ method. This method consists in the inclusion of CNC during the synthesis of WBPUU, and more precisely during the phase inversion step by taking advantage of the hydrophilic nature of CNC. As indicated previously, the inclusion of nanoentities into inks for DIW 3D-printing was extensively studied in the literature (Hung et al. 2016). However, most of the published works present materials with addition of CNC or other nanoentities ex situ, i.e. after the synthesis, presenting a slight modification of rheological parameters (Gutierrez et al. 2019), whereas the number of works using a in situ addition method of CNC is scarce. Additionally, some authors claimed that anisotropic nanoentities such as CNC can be aligned during extrusion using DIW (Lewis 2006; Feilden et al. 2017; Siqueira et al. 2017), expecting an enhancement of the mechanical properties of the final printed piece. The different synthesized inks with in situ added CNC different contents were extensively characterized from the rheological viewpoint. Finally, the printed pieces from WBPUU based inks with different amounts of CNC were also characterized from the physicochemical, mechanical and thermomechanical viewpoints in order to study the influence of CNC as reinforcement, apart from in the rheology.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Materials

WBPUU inks were synthesized using two difunctional polyols as soft segment: polyethyleneglycol diol (PEG) and polycaprolactone diol (PCL) (molecular weight from the supplier $M_n = 1000$ and 2000 g mol^{-1} , respectively), both provided by Sigma-Aldrich. Regarding the hard segment (HS), it is formed by 2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl) propionic acid (DMPA, 98% purity), ethylene diamine (EDA, 99% purity), used as internal emulsifier and chain extender respectively, provided also by Sigma-Aldrich, and isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI, 99.5% purity), kindly supplied from Covestro. Triethylamine (TEA, 99.5% purity) was used as neutralizer of the carboxylic groups of DMPA (provided by Fluka) whereas dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTDL), provided by Sigma-Aldrich, was used as catalyst. Both the polyols and the DMPA were dried under vacuum at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h prior to their use. Butanone (99.5% purity), supplied by Panreac, was used to transfer the neutralized DMPA into the reaction medium and also adjust

viscosity. Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) provided by the University of Maine (Lot. 2018-FPL-CNC-117 and Sulfur content of 1.0 wt% from the data sheet of the supplier) were used as reinforcement.

Synthesis of the WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites based inks

The synthesis of the WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites have been carried out using a 250 mL four-necked flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer, thermometer, condenser, and nitrogen inlet within a thermostated bath. WBPUU with a PCL:PEG molar ratio of 0.8:0.2 has been synthesized according to the methodology proposed in a previous work (Vadillo et al. 2020). The synthesis involves two steps. In the first one PCL, PEG and IPDI reacted in bulk under the presence of 0.1 wt% of DBTL at 80 °C for 3 h. After cooling to 50 °C, DMPA previously neutralized with TEA and diluted in 5 mL of butanone was added and left to react for 1 h. In the second step, the system is cooled at room temperature and the phase inversion is carried out by adding deionized water (DI) drop by drop under vigorous stirring. Finally, EDA is added as chain extender previously dissolved in DI drop by drop at 35 °C, letting the system 2 h so as to ensure that the chain extender has reacted with the remaining free isocyanate groups. Each step reaction progress was evaluated by dibutylamine back titration method according to ASTM D 2572–97. The molar ratio of PCL, PEG, DMPA, IPDI and EDA was 0.8:0.2:1:3.5:1.5. The inks based on WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites with different cellulose contents, varying from 0.25 to 2 wt% respect to the WBPUU, were prepared adding the CNC in situ during the synthesis of the nanocomposite. Concretely, the CNC, previously dispersed in DI, were added during the phase inversion step. The solid content of the nanocomposites was fixed to 29 wt%. In the next part, each sample will be named as WBPUUX where X corresponds to the wt% of CNC.

Extrusion based 3D-printing of prepared inks

The synthesized WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC inks were printed by DIW 3D-printing technology using a modification of a conventional fused deposition modeling (FDM) Voladora 3D-printing machine, provided by Tumaker (Spain) in order to adapt the equipment to the DIW 3D-printing. Samples were printed through a needle of 0.8 mm of diameter with a printing speed of 6 mm·s⁻¹. This needle diameter allowed a homogeneous extrusion of the ink with high definition of the printing object. Despite a wide range of diameters are reported in the literature, similar diameters have been also observed in other works (Su et al. 2019; Oliveira et al. 2020). Prior to the printing, all samples were loaded into the syringes and centrifuged for 3 min at 3000 rpm to homogenize the ink and to remove the existing bubbles. The maximum shear rate on the needle wall was calculated using the Weissenberg–Rabinowitsch–Mooney Eq. (1) for non-Newtonian fluids (Calafel et al. 2020), obtaining a shear rate in the range of 30–50 s⁻¹ for all studied systems.

$$\dot{\gamma}_{max} = \frac{4\dot{Q}}{\pi r^3} \left(\frac{3n+1}{4n} \right) \quad (1)$$

where r is the needle internal radius, n is the flow index of the fluid and \dot{Q} the flow rate calculated as $\dot{Q} = Sr^2$ with S as the printing speed in mm s⁻¹.

All samples were printed in dog bone shape according to ISO 527. Strips were also printed with 2.8 mm in width and 0.5 mm in thickness for mechanical and thermomechanical tests. Regarding the printing pattern direction, the deposition of the ink has been carried out parallel to the longer

axis of both strips and dog bone shapes. As it is claimed by some authors, the direction of the deposition of the ink containing nanoentities has influence in the reinforcement effect (Siqueira et al. 2017), so it is expected that the improvement of the mechanical properties will be higher in a parallel disposition rather than with a perpendicular one. Printed pieces were dried at room temperature for 48 h before physico-chemical, thermal, thermomechanical and mechanical characterization. As a result, all samples showed a decrease of their height due to the water removal. Additionally, in order to study the internal structure of printed pieces, some samples were printed in form of cylinders, frozen, and subsequently freeze-dried ($-60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 0.1 Pa during 48 h) so as to obtain porous scaffolds. The dimension of the printed pieces (d_1 : upper diameter, d_2 : lower diameter and a : height) were measured in order to evaluate the shape fidelity comparing with the CAD model (1 mm of diameter and 5 mm of height).

Characterization

Characterization of materials

The characteristic functional groups of CNC and WBPUU and hydrogen bonding interactions in WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites were analyzed by FTIR using a Nicolet Nexus spectrometer provided with a MKII Golden Gate accessory (Specac) with a diamond crystal at a nominal incidence angle of 45° and ZnSe lens. Spectra were recorded in attenuated reflection (ATR) mode between 4000 and 650 cm^{-1} averaging 64 scans with a resolution of 8 cm^{-1} .

The thermal stability of WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites was analyzed by TGA using a Mettler Toledo equipment. Between 5 and 10 mg of sample were introduced in ceramic pans. The sample was heated from 25 to $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in nitrogen atmosphere at a scanning rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$. From the weight loss and its derivative (DTG) curves, the initial degradation temperature (T_0) as the loss of 5% of the initial weight, and the maximum degradation temperatures (T_{d1} and T_{d2}) as the minimum of the degradation peaks in the derivative of thermogravimetric curve were determined.

Tensile tests of the printed pieces were performed on an Instron 5967 universal testing machine provided with a 500 N load cell and pneumatic grips to hold the samples. Samples printed in strip shape were tested at a constant rate of 20 mm min^{-1} at room temperature with a distance between clamps of 10 mm. Young modulus (E), stress at break (r_b) and strain at break (e_b) were averaged from stress-strain curves of three specimens of each system.

The thermomechanical behavior of the samples printed in strips shape was determined by using an Eplexor 100 N analyzer Gabo equipment. The measurements were carried out in tensile mode from -100 to $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a constant scanning rate of $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$, a fixed frequency equal to 1 Hz, and a constant strain fixed at 0.05% to be in the linear viscoelastic domain. So as to study the morphology of prepared WBPUU-CNC scaffolds, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) measurements were performed by a Field Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscope (FEG-SEM) Hitachi S-4800 N, at a voltage of 5 kV. Prior to the test, and in order to analyse the cross-section of prepared scaffolds, the samples were cryo-fractured in liquid nitrogen, so as to avoid the deformation of the scaffolds during the cutting process, and sputter-coated with a thin layer of gold ($\sim 10\text{ nm}$) in a Emitech K550X ion-sputter.

Rheological characterization of inks

Rheological characterization of the inks was carried out using a R101 model (Anton Paar), provided by a temperature chamber and solvent trap. Flow tests were performed at 22.5 °C using a plate–plate geometry of 50 mm as a shear rate sweep from 0.01 to 120 s⁻¹. To evaluate the yield point determination, dynamic oscillatory tests were performed in a shear stress range of 0.09–1500 Pa at 22.5 °C in a plate–plate geometry of 25 mm. To determine linear domain, the strain sweep tests were performed at 22.5 °C at a fixed frequency of 1 Hz varying the strain from 0.01 to 200%. Frequency sweep tests, from 0.01 to 10 Hz, were performed in the linear domain, at 22.5 °C and at a fixed strain equal to 1%. Finally, structure recovery tests were performed at 22.5 °C in a three stage test, (i) the viscosity was measured at 1 s⁻¹ during 10 s, (ii) the shear rate was fixed at 100 s⁻¹ and the viscosity was measured during 10 s, (iii) the shear rate was fixed again at 1 s⁻¹ and the viscosity was measured during 3 min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characterization of materials

The main functional groups of neat components and the hydrogen bonding interactions between CNC and WBPUU matrix in the nanocomposites were studied by FTIR. Figure 1 shows the spectra of nanocomposites and neat components. In the nanocomposites, a single band was observed in the 3600–3100 cm⁻¹ interval, which is also observed in the WBPUU matrix and is assigned to the N–H stretching vibration of urethane group (Gao et al. 2012). This band also englobes the observed one for the CNC, which is attributed to O–H stretching vibration. Regarding the carbonyl region, which is situated between 1800 and 1600 cm⁻¹ and is shown in the inset of Fig. 2, a displacement towards lower wavenumber in the stretching vibration of C=O group can be observed. In the case of the WBPUU matrix the C=O band appeared at 1735 cm⁻¹, but in the WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites this band is shifted towards lower wavenumbers as the CNC content increased, suggesting the existence of hydrogen bonding interactions between WBPUU and CNC (Santamaria-Echart et al. 2016b).

The thermal stability of the CNC, WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites was studied by TGA. The weight loss as well as the derivative thermogravimetric curves are displayed in Fig. 2.

The WBPUU matrix showed a two-step degradation process, as was observed in previous work (Vadillo et al. 2020), which can be observed also in all the WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites. The former, which also present a shoulder at lower temperatures, can be attributed to urea and urethane groups degradation respectively, whereas the latter is assigned to the polyols degradation. Studying the initial degradation and the maximum degradation temperatures, which are displayed into Table 1, a significant increase of the initial degradation temperature and Td1 (both shoulder and peak) values was observed in the nanocomposites. The increase of the thermal stability with the addition of CNC can be attributed to the stabilization of urea and urethane groups by interactions of the WBPUU matrix and the CNC through chemical bonding, as also observed by FTIR.

In order to study the integration of the CNC reinforcement in the WBPUU particles, as well as the resulting interactions, the WBPUU and WBPUU- CNC nanocomposite dispersions were studied by TEM. Images of the WBPUU and WBPUU + 0.5% CNC are shown in Fig. 3. WBPUU

matrix showed a homogeneous distribution of particles, with no presence of agglomerates. WBPUU-CNC, contrary, presented agglomeration of particles with no presence of free cellulose, suggesting that these nanoentities are embedded into the particles. This observation would confirm the proposed integration of the CNC into the polyurethane particles proposed by Chen et al. (2019), where the nanoentity, in this case cellulose nanofibers (CNF), reacts with the polyurethane prepolymer in an early stage of the synthesis, concretely during the phase inversion, resulting into a chemical bonding between the aforementioned CNF and the polymer backbone. This inclusion of the nanoentities in the polyurethane particles could modify the rheological properties of the WBPUU-CNC inks in a different way than to the addition is carried out after the synthesis, resulting as well in the obtaining of a final material with different thermal, mechanical and thermomechanical properties.

Rheological characterization and 3D-printing of WBPUU-CNC inks

In order to study the viscosity of the prepared WBPUU-CNC based inks, flow test was performed at increasing shear rate. The obtained viscosity curves are displayed in Fig. 4. Both WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC inks showed a decrease of the viscosity as the shear rate increases, which is known as a shear thinning behaviour. It is assumed that as the shear rate increased, the network of the hydrogel weakens leading to the decrease in the viscosity and also to the loose of the entrapped liquid. The addition of CNC to the WBPUU ink did not seem to modify this behaviour which has been observed for other printable systems in the literature and is desirable for a successful printing performance (Guvendiren et al. 2012; Markstedt et al. 2015; Siqueira et al. 2017). As can be observed the incorporation of CNC results in an increase of the viscosity as the CNC content increases. As expected, we observe the increase of the viscosity at 0.01 s^{-1} with CNC addition. WBPUU-CNC inks presented a viscosity range of 11,434–25,101 Pa.s at 0.01 s^{-1} in contrast with the 3851 Pa.s obtained for WBPUU matrix. Contrary, at the shear rate corresponding to the printing performance ($30\text{--}50 \text{ s}^{-1}$) the composites inks showed a low viscosity in the range of 32.2–62.4 Pa.s whereas the matrix presented a 19.3 Pa.s showing smaller differences between matrix and composites compared with the ones observed at 0.01 s^{-1} . Additionally, the addition of CNC resulted in a decrease of the extent of the Newtonian plateau, as well as to an increase of the viscosity value of the plateau. The extent of this plateau decreases progressively as the CNC content increases, starting the shear thinning region at lower shear rates, until to its completely disappearance at CNC contents above 1 wt%.

Spectromechanical analysis were performed with increasing shear stress to determine the yield point (Fig. 5). In order to study the influence of the CNC into the printability of the inks, the yield point of the different systems were determined using the method proposed by Cyriac et al. (the yield point is determined by measuring the stress at which the deviation of the linearity of the storage modulus is produced) (Cyriac et al. 2015). Additionally, the flow point of the inks was calculated as the crossover between G' and G'' in order to study the behaviour of the material during its breakdown. For that purpose, “flow transition index” (FTI) was determined as the ratio between flow point and yield point (Corker et al. 2019).

Analyzing the obtained results, which are displayed Table 2, an increase of both yield and flow point with the increase of the CNC content was observed. The yield point presented a continuous increase with the CNC content lower than 1 wt%. From 1 wt% of CNC, the inks exhibits a higher increase of the yield point as already observed in the literature (Minas et al. 2016; Zhang et al.

2020). This behaviour can lead posteriorly to problems of extrudability in the DIW 3D printer due to higher pressure to extrude the WBPUU-CNC inks through the nozzle, resulting in an inconstant and inhomogeneous thread. Additionally, the yield point also has influenced as far as shape fidelity is concerned, presenting systems with very low yield points troubles to maintain the given form, flowing after being printed and collapsing owing to the weight of the 3D multilayered construct. Regarding the FTI index, no difference between different contents of cellulose was observed, and comparing with the matrix a small decrease is observed, suggesting that the addition of CNC do not has a strong influence into the brittleness of the ink, at least with low CNC content.

The experimental data of the flow curves were adjusted to the Herschel–Bulkley model so as to describe the experimental data and study the influence of the CNC into the ink. An example of the adjustment of the experimental flow curve to the proposed model is displayed into Figure S1, whereas the obtained values from the adjustment are listed in Table 2. Comparing the experimental data with the predicted model, a good correlation was observed. The results, showed an increasing value of the consistency index (K) as the CNC content increased, leading to higher consistency of the material for systems presenting higher CNC content, which can hence, result into the extrusion problems of the material during 3D-printing or result in a poor printing performance (Liu et al. 2017). Regarding flow index (n), all systems showed values under 1, which confirms the aforementioned shearthinning behaviour, which is desirable for a successful 3D-printing (Costakis et al. 2016).

Strain sweep tests were performed for the different WBPUU-CNC composites in order to determine the linear viscoelastic region (LVR) of the prepared inks (Figure S2). Analyzing the obtained results, it was noticed that at low strain values both the storage and the loss moduli were independent of the strain amplitude. For all samples, even pure matrix, G' remains higher than G'' . The matrix is like a gel, confirmed by the frequency sweep, and the fillers increase the elasticity by filler effect.

Frequency sweep tests were also performed fixing the strain value to 1% to determine both storage and loss moduli of the hydrogels and thus, analyze the structural integrity of the inks. The measured G' and G'' at different frequencies are displayed into Fig. 6 whereas values measured at 1 Hz of G' , G'' and $\tan \delta$ are displayed in Table S1. It can be seen that the CNC act successfully as a reinforcement of the gel network leading to more structured printed pieces. Analyzing the obtained results, systems containing higher CNC content presented higher values of both storage and loss moduli as was observed in oscillatory strain test. According to the literature, a phenomenological relationship can be established between the storage modulus and the stability: a G' higher than 103 Pa is necessary to support high stable 3D structure of multiple layers (Li et al. 2019). All the systems included the WBPUU matrix presented storage modulus above this value. In the same time, Álvarez-Castillo et al. establish a limit of storage modulus for good printing performance for a plasma protein based doughs where systems having both viscoelastic moduli below 103 Pa and over 105 Pa were too weak to keep the shape or too stiff to be properly extruded, respectively (Alvarez-Castillo et al. 2021). According to this, all systems presented storage modulus values in the range of successful printing performance.

Regarding the $\tan \delta$, the inclusion of CNC into the WBPUU inks resulted in a decrease of the

aforementioned $\tan \delta$ from 0.29 to 0.2 at 1 Hz, illustrating a swipe towards a more solid-like behaviour for the composites. However, comparing the different prepared WBPUU-CNC compositions, the addition of higher amounts of CNC do not affect the $\tan \delta$, obtaining for all systems $\tan \delta$ values between 0.17 and 0.2. The decrease of the $\tan \delta$ observed with the addition to the matrix of CNC is correlated to a turning to a more elastic one, which leads to systems presenting a better shape fidelity. However, a too elastic material can be counterproductive, presenting problems of cohesion between layers if the aforementioned $\tan \delta$ is too low.

According to the literature, more than 80% of recovery is desirable for 3D-printing (Peak et al. 2017), To confirm the viability of inks studied for DIW 3D-printing, the recovery was studied and results are displayed in Fig. 7. WBPUU \pm 0.25%CNC and WBPUU \pm 0.5%CNC nanocomposites, showed 91 and 89% of recovery respectively, higher values compared to the WBPUU matrix (84%). Regarding the composites presenting CNC contents above 1 wt%, contrary to the behaviour observed for nanocomposites with lower CNC content, a drastic decrease of the recovery was observed, up to 74% due to the slipping of the material out of the geometry of the rheometer during the test because of its too elastic behaviour. The calculated recovery values are displayed in Table S1.

All WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites have been printed by DIW 3D-printing obtaining dog bone shaped pieces for all the systems until 1 wt% of CNC (Fig. 8). In the supplementary material, a video of a part of the printing performance of a dog bone shaped piece of the WBPUU0.5 systems is shown (view online resource 1). Systems containing more amount of CNC presented a too high storage modulus to be printed, despite presenting yield point values in the range of printing. WBPUU1 was printed, but presented homogeneity problems in the printed thread, due to its too elastic behaviour showing also a poor cohesion capacity as was also observed in the literature for very low values of $\tan \delta$ (Perez et al. 2015). However, WBPUU0.25 and WBPUU0.5 presented good printability and better appearance if compared with the pure WBPUU matrix, especially as far as shape fidelity is concerned. Despite the matrix presents a good printability, the shape fidelity was not still acceptable, concretely in the borders of the piece.

The shape fidelity of the printed parts was quantitatively evaluated by comparing the dimensions of simple pieces such as cylinders with those of the CAD design. For that purpose, WBPUU, WBPUU0.25 and WBPUU0.5 were printed in cylindrical form and their dimensions (d_1 : upper diameter, d_2 : lower diameter and a : height) were measured. The results, which are presented in Fig. 9, showed that the WBPUU system presented bad shape fidelity, showing an increase of the d_2 and a decrease of the height and the d_1 compared with the CAD design as a result of the collapsing of the structure and spreading of the material. Both systems containing cellulose contrary, demonstrated better capacity to maintain the shape presenting similar values than the CAD design after printing. Concretely the WBPUU0.5 system presented the best results, showing a higher shape fidelity to the CAD design.

The addition of CNC strongly participates keeping the given shape. This increase of the rheological parameters such as viscosity and storage modulus resulted higher compared to the values observed in the literature for WBPU-CNC systems prepared ex situ for such a small amount of CNC. In this case, the early addition of CNC, could lead, as was proposed by Chen et al., 2019,

to the formation of a chemical bonding between the CNC and the WBPUU prepolymer, through some of the NCO free groups of the prepolymer which were formulated for the posterior extension by EDA. Notwithstanding, the temperature during the phase inversion is reduced to avoid side reactions with water, and hence, also with the OH of CNC. However, with high amounts of CNC this reaction is more likely to occur, leading to a greater increase of rheological parameters such as viscosity and storage modulus than was expected.

Morphology of the printed pieces

In order to analyze the structuration of the inks provided by the addition of CNC, electron scanning microscopy was used so as to obtain images of the morphology of the prepared scaffolds via freeze-drying technique of the cylinders. Heterogeneous morphology can be observed for the WBPUU based scaffold as reported in Fig. 10. The viscous behaviour of this ink is not able to support a multi-layered 3D construct, resulting in the collapse of the structure which results in the aforementioned heterogeneous morphology. Regarding the systems containing CNC, both WBPUU + 0.25% CNC and WBPUU + 0.5% CNC, presented a homogeneous morphology. In this case, the printed inks are able to support the weight of the upper layers, allowing to obtain multi-layered ordered systems which result, after the freeze-drying, into a homogenous morphology. Additionally, the obtained morphology in all scaffolds, confirmed a good cohesion between printed layers demonstrating their viability for DIW 3D-printing.

Mechanical and thermomechanical characterization of printed pieces

The influence of the in situ incorporated cellulose nanocrystals on the mechanical properties of the printed pieces has been studied by tensile test. Strip shape solid printed pieces of WBPUU, WBPUU0.25 and WBPUU0.5 were analyzed. Young modulus, stress and strain at break were determined from stress– strain curves which are reported in Table 3. Systems with CNC content higher than 0.5 wt% did not result in recognizable strip pieces.

The results showed that the incorporation of CNC into the WBPUU matrix contributes to increase the stiffness of the printed pieces. The Young modulus of the final material increases up to almost ten times when 0.5 wt% of CNC is added to the ink, concretely from 14 to 120 MPa. Contrary, the elongation at break decreases with the increase of CNC content, more noticeably for the system containing 0.5 wt% of CNC, which experienced a decrease of the elongation at break from 1303 to 979%. Comparing these results with the ones observed in the literature for ex situ prepared similar WBPU-CNC systems, to obtain a similar increase of the Young modulus, Liu et al. reported a CNC content of 5 wt% (Liu et al. 2013), whereas other authors obtained a smaller increase of the Young modulus with similar quantities of cellulose derived reinforcements (Santamaria-Echart et al. 2016a; Chen et al. 2019).

Regarding the thermomechanical properties, the evolution of storage modulus (E') and $\tan \delta$ with temperature of the different WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites and the WBPUU matrix are shown in Fig. 11. As can be observed, the addition of CNC resulted in an increase of the E' in the whole temperature interval owing to the reinforcement effect of the nanocrystals (Rueda et al. 2013). In the glassy-state, between -80 °C and -60 °C, E' modulus exhibits higher values, around 2600–2800 MPa for nanocomposites due to the reinforcing effect of CNC. At higher temperatures, a decrease for E' was observed, usually reflected by a peak in $\tan \delta$ curve, which

is related with the material's glass transition temperature (Cakic' et al. 2014). Tan δ peak is shifted slightly to higher temperature and decreases in intensity with the increase of CNC content, indicative of the effective interactions between matrix and CNC, as were also observed by FTIR, which hinder chain mobility (Wu et al. 2007). At higher temperatures, nanocomposites, especially the WBPUU0.5, exhibits higher E' and its decrease, associated with the disruption of intermolecular associations and starting of the flow (Chen et al. 2019), shifted clearly to higher temperature, is the demonstration of an enhancement of the thermomechanical stability. These reinforcing effects and chain mobility restrictions corroborate that CNC interact effectively with the matrix in agreement with FTIR, TGA and mechanical properties results.

Conclusions

In this work, the role of in situ added cellulose nanocrystals as viscosity modulator was investigated in order to improve the printing performance of a novel waterborne polyurethane urea based ink synthesized with a combination of hydrophobic PCL and hydrophilic PEG in the soft segment for DIW 3D- printing. For this purpose, the incorporation of low contents of cellulosic filler during the synthesis has been studied as a design strategy in order to improve the printing performances. To tune the better formulation, an extensive rheological analysis has been carried out to the different ink formulations, which were subsequently printed so as to study their final appearance and shape fidelity, and hence, establish a correlation between the rheological analysis and the printing performances.

All the studied inks showed a shear-thinning behaviour, confirming their suitability for DIW 3D- printing. Moreover, the in situ addition of CNC during the synthesis of the ink, maintaining the solid content constant and equal to 29 wt%, showed a precise modification of the rheological parameters showing a gradual increase as the CNC content increased. The addition of CNC to the inks did not modify the observed shear-thinning behaviour in the WBPUU, and also led into an increase of both viscosity and yield point. Regarding shape fidelity, the inclusion of small amounts of CNC in situ (0.25 or 0.5 wt%), led to higher storage modulus and lower tan δ values, which improved the capacity of the ink to support multiple layers and to maintain the given shape after printing. Moreover, it should be highlighted the positive effect on the printing performance of slight variations of storage modulus and tan δ . Compared to WBPUU (G' of 1618 Pa and tan δ of 0.22), WBPUU0.25 (G' of 2073 Pa and tan δ of 0.20) and WBPUU0.5 (G' of 2218 Pa and tan δ of 0.18) showed better shape fidelity. Additionally, the addition of CNC to the prepared inks, resulted in a remarkable increase of the stiffness and the thermomechanical stability of the final printed pieces, acting as a reinforcement of the final material. This increase is higher compared with the one obtained in the literature for ex situ added reinforcements, requiring in those cases much more quantity of CNC to obtain similar increases. Finally, as was corroborated by SEM, the in situ addition of CNC resulted into a higher structuration of the printed piece, being able to support the weight of the multilayered construct without collapsing. Regarding the advantages of the in situ method, among the possibility of adding hydrophilic nanoentities during the process, as well as its greater influence in the mechanical properties; rheological wise, a smaller quantity of reinforcement is needed compared with ex situ method so as to obtain the needed rheological parameters which lead to the obtaining of suitable inks. Cellulose nanocrystals have demonstrated to be a useful additive which can

improve the printability and shape fidelity of 3D constructs, as well as to improve the mechanical and thermomechanical stability of the resulting piece.

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Figure list

Graphical abstract

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of WBPUU, CNC and WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites. In the inset 1800-1600 cm^{-1} region.

Fig. 2. TGA curves (up) and DTG curves (down) of WBP UU and WBP UU-CNC nanocomposites.

Fig. 3. TEM images of inks at different magnifications: a) WBPUU x 20000, b) WBPUU x 50000, c) WBPUU0.5 x 20000 and d) WBPUU0.5 x 50000 (Circles: cellulose nanocrystals and Inset: magnification of the CNC nanoentities in contact with the particles).

Fig. 4. Viscosity as a function of shear rate ($T = 22.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) of WBP UU and WBP UU-CNC nanocomposites

Fig. 5. (—) Storage and (---) loss moduli as a function of shear stress at 1 Hz. Yield point determination of WBP UU and WBP UU-CNC composites ($T = 22.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). (○) Yield point, (☆) Flow point

Fig. 6. G' (filled square) and G'' (square) as a function of frequency ($T = 22.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) of WBPUU-CNC inks

Fig. 7. Structure recovery test of WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC based inks ($T = 22.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Fig. 8. Printed pieces of WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC composites

Fig. 9. Printed pieces of WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC composites in cylindrical form and comparison with the CAD model

Fig. 10. SEM images of the different WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC scaffolds

Fig. 11. (—) Storage modulus and (---) $\tan \delta$ as a function of temperature for WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites. Frequency = 1 Hz and scanning rate = 2 °C min⁻¹

Table list

Table 1. Initial degradation and maximum degradation temperatures of WBPUU matrix and WBPUU-CNC nanocomposites.

System	T ₀ (°C)	Td ₁ (°C)	Td ₂ (°C)
WBPUU	250	245, 312	404
WBPUU0.25	256	247, 320	402
WBPUU0.5	264	251, 339	397
WBPUU1	277	260, 361	399
WBPUU2	281	260, 364	399

Table 2. Yield point, flow point, flow transition index and parameters obtained from the adjustment to Herschel-Bulkley model ($\sigma - \sigma_y = K\dot{\gamma}^n$) of WBPUU and WBPUU-CNC inks with different CNC content.

System	Yield point (Pa)	Flow point (Pa)	FTI	Herschel-Bulkley model		
				K Index (Pa·s n ⁻¹)	n index	R ²
WBPUU	44	562	13	177.1	0.15	0.92
WBPUU0.25	70	1056	12	276.9	0.12	0.94
WBPUU0.5	94	1061	11	335.5	0.18	0.90
WBPUU1	114	1344	12	369.1	0.17	0.91
WBPUU2	150	1689	11	606.1	0.19	0.97

Table 3. Mechanical properties of printed pieces.

System	Young modulus (MPa)	Stress at break (MPa)	Strain at break (%)
WBPUU	14 ± 1	16 ± 2	1303 ± 35
WBPUU0.25	17 ± 1	15 ± 1	1120 ± 49
WBPUU0.5	120 ± 6	10 ± 1	979 ± 40